

FEATURES OF LANDSCAPE CREATION IN IMPRESSIONISM

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Abstract. *In this article, impressionism is a creative movement that arose at the end of the 19th century and combines the creativity of many artists of the world. The characteristic feature of the work of the representatives of this movement is to sing the nature of the motherland and to arouse love for it in people. and it is highlighted that it acquires uniqueness due to the richness of the air.*

Keywords: *impressionism, fine art, landscape art.*

INTRODUCTION

One of the main topics of fine art is to express the owners of professions and their hard work through color images. The weighty and lively lifestyle of ordinary life is considered one of the directions of French national realistic landscape art impressionism. An important role was played by the creativity of artists who made Barbizon near Paris and its surrounding lands, the Fontainebleau forest, their favorite place. Based on the observation and deep study of the nature of their country, they created works typical of the landscape genre, which are not large in terms of size, and showed the beauty of nature to many people. expressed their love and respect for the country. They tried to express their feelings and moods in landscape art. They created works directly in nature.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS

Impressionism as a great creative movement that emerged at the end of the 19th century unites the creativity of many brush masters of the world. In particular, its genesis began in French visual arts, in the works of dozens of famous farang artists such as Van Gogh, Paul Gauguin, Edgar Degas, Edward Manet, Camille Corot, Gustave Courbet, Pierre Renoir, Claude Monet, Paul Cézanne, Henri de Toulouse-Lortec, Georges Seurat. must be recognized as having matured. The representatives of this movement moved away from the traditions of classicism and romanticism to a new stage of making an impression in the world of color. Edouard Manet was one of the first artists who started this way. At a young age, Manet entered visual art with a special look, and while he surprised most of the contemporary artists with his new views, he caused objections to many more. Today, Edouard Manet's works are an art that has gained a special position with its theme and style of expression and is finding its value.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The phrase "Barbizon school" is used to describe the work of representatives of the French national realistic school from the 3rd to the 40th years. The characteristic feature of the work of the representatives of this school is to sing the nature of the motherland, to arouse love for it in people. Their works are directly taken from life itself, and the composition and color It is characterized by its abundance of natural light and air.

Theodore Rousseau (1812-1867) is a well-known representative of the Barbizon school. He depicts nature in a calm, peaceful and majestic way. This artist likes to depict wide open spaces, forest edges, trunks of large oak trees clinging to the ground with strong roots, sometimes in the open, in the sun, sometimes before sunset. In the works of Jules Dupre (1811 - 1889), the

turbulent nature, cooperation is encouraged. The artist reflects the natural scenes during his work, the fiery temperature of the setting sun, and when he works on the image of ponds and lakes, the clouds floating in the sky are reflected on their surface. Morning work, quiet evening poetry by Sharl It found expression in the work of Francois Daubini (1817-1878). Rass loves to depict riverbanks. In his works, a peaceful life is expressed in the use of elegant colors. Narpissa Diaz (1807-1676) is another representative of the Barbizon school. It works on the appearance of thick forests, their fields and fields. His scenes are bright and decorative. The sunlight coming down from among the trees increases the color contrast and shimmer in his works.

Depicting the life and work of ordinary people is the content of the works of great French artists F. Mille and G. Courbet. One of Millet's famous works is his painting "Women Gathering Ears" (1657). The image of women gathering ears of wheat left in the field after the harvest shows the hardships of peasant labor. G. Courbet tried to reveal the changes taking place in social life in his works. He is a major artist of Western Europe of the 19th century. "The path of democratic art is realism," said Courbet. He remained faithful to his words until the end of his life. Courbet described the events that surrounded him, which only he knew. The painting "The Burial in Ornan" is one of such works. The plot of the painting is made directly from reality, and each image depicted in it is familiar to the artist and they are people who have their own world view. By showing their character and attitude to the happenings, the artist managed to clearly express the idea of the work that people are becoming less human. His slogan "We demand modernity from artists" found its expression in the work of the advanced artists of the next period.

Manet did not choose painting but painting chose him, that is, fine art was a naturally gifted path. His father, like other noble families, wanted his son Eduard to become an official and even forced him to become a lawyer. However, when nothing came of it, in 1850 he was apprenticed to Tom Courture, a well-known artist of his time. In the years before that, the future artist was influenced by the works in the Louvre and searched. Agreed to study at a seafaring school, failed the exam, worked on the sailing ship "Houvre and Guadeloupe" and admired what he saw during his trip to Brazil - exotic natural landscapes, southern women in sketches. The paintings he worked on dispelled his father's doubts that Eduard would really be an artist. While the artist was studying at Courture's workshop, he began to reject the bourgeois theme, the classical-romantic traditions, which were leading the French visual arts. Due to his critical views, his relationship with Tom Couture deteriorated and he was expelled from his workshop. He returns again with his father's actions.

His anti-academic paintings "Balcony", "Beer in a cup", "Breakfast on the meadow", "Olympia" were created at the same time. These works were criticized by the press and many artists, so his new views were strongly defended by Edgar Degas, Paul Cézanne, Claude Monet.

In 1856-58, Manet's reputation increased, and various salons demanded his works. Satisfied with his research, in 1859 he presented his work for the first time to the prestigious exhibition held annually at the Paris Salon. With great hopes, he presents his painting in a realistic style called "Maykhor" to the exhibition. Couture also left his workshop after he had a negative reaction to his work. He broke off his relationship with him and rented a separate workshop. He participated in the Franco-Prussian war in 1870-71. Even in those difficult moments, he works on port scenes without giving up his creativity.

Musavvir's painting "Maykhor" is one of his later famous works, in which the subject is clearly and vividly depicted in a realistic form without excessive exaggeration. The object of the

May devotee is a man seated, with a cup filled with May and an empty bottle of May on the ground. There is no sarcasm or innuendo in the picture. In expressing the situation, the background did not use the halftone technique, but separated the figure from the background with a light shade. A different approach is taken in shading, and it is not expressed in exactly the same way as the figure.

By 1977, the artist focused on creating works in the genres of still life and portraiture. The formation of his original style was significantly influenced by the work of the famous artist of the 16th century, Diego Rodríguez de Silva Velázquez, and Manet was very interested in the works of this Spanish painter.

Despite the setbacks, Mane's quest has come to light. He is looking for new subjects for the work. After the works "Music in the Tuileries Garden", "Portrait of Parents", "Gitarerro" were created, his work began to be recognized in the press. The acceptance of his work into salons brings Eduard prestige and money.

CONCLUSION

Representatives of Impressionism strived to depict the existing being in motion and change in a more natural way, to express their momentary impressions, and achieved vividness and truthfulness of the image. The naturalness of reality, its constant change was expressed in the unity of man and environment. The strength and purity of the first impressions, the unique features were described by the artists in the landscape, portrait, and multi-form compositions without going into small details. time, Impressionists created colorful views of modern city life and reflected its uniqueness in the form of cityscapes and people in their works.

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